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HALFWAY THROUGH THE 2030 AGENDA, GENDER EQUALITY PROGRESSES SLOWLY.

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Policy Statement

The fifth Sustainable Development Goal (SDG 5) as part of the United Nations (UN) 2030 Agenda addresses gender equality. Comprising five goals and three sub-goals with their indicators and sub-indicators, SDG 5 proposes to: "Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls." (UN BR, 2015) On the one hand, eliminating gender discrimination and violence by 2030 is central to SDG 5; on the other hand, achieving this Goal is also strategic for advancing the other 16 Goals that complete the Agenda mentioned above agreed upon by the 193 UN member countries. So, achieving SDG 5 is strategic because, among other no less relevant reasons, according to the World Bank (2024), if we all successfully eliminate discriminatory or restrictive laws and practices against women in the labor market, global GDP would increase by more than 20%, with a profound positive impact on the growth rate in the 2030s. However, the achievement of SDG 5 seems increasingly distant. Judging by the indices published in the 2023 Gender Panorama (United Nations, 2023a), the goals are primarily challenging, and the global impact of this challenge cannot be overstated.

Background

In general terms, access to education for girls and boys has been increasing. However, in 2022, 32.1% of young women aged 15 to 24 were neither studying nor receiving any training or employed. This percentage among young men of the same age group was 15.4%. Within this universe, the UN recorded the most significant disparity in Central and Southern Asia, where the rate among the mentioned group of women was 48.7% vis-à-vis 15.4% among their male counterparts.

In 2019, on average worldwide, for every dollar men earned in formal jobs, women earned 51 cents. Thus, women's participation in the total resources from the labor market was only 34%. Considering regional individualities, this reality was even more alarming. While in Europe and North America, women received 64 cents for every dollar paid to men that year, this value dropped to 21 cents in Central and Southern Asia. (United Nations, 2023, p. 18).

Three years later, in 2022, less than 2/3 of women in their peak productive age, i.e., between 25 and 54 years, were employed, according to the United Nations publication (2023, p. 18). Precisely, it was 61.4% compared to 90.6% of men of the same age group.

Adopting regional peculiarities as we did in the paragraph dedicated to 2019, we observe that despite being 57% more educated than men using higher education as a parameter, in the European Union (EU), the employment rate for women reached 83.6%, while that of their male counterparts was 88.9%. Unlike the cut the United Nations uses, these percentages refer to individuals between 15 and 64 years old. Among salaries, the difference was 12.7%, indicating a drop of 3.7 percentage points between 2012 and 2022. Still, each euro paid to a man equaled just under 88 euro cents paid to a woman. Despite the variations that everyone can check in the original publication, Luxembourg was the only EU country where women's salaries were, on average, 0.7% higher than men's. (Yanatma 2024).

Findings

In truth, according to the United Nations (UN), the 193 member countries had yet to achieve the goals of SDG 5 by 2023. The Organization informs that only 15.4% of the fifth Goal's indicators are heading in the right direction, while 61.5% are near halfway, and 23.1% are far or very far from the goals set for 2030 (United Nations, 2023b).

Given the slow progress on some SDG 5 indicators, the UN (2023b) infers that it will take 286 years to close the legal protection gaps for women and repeal discriminatory laws against them, 140 years for equal representation in positions of power and leadership in the workplace, and 47 years to achieve equality in the rates of parliamentary seats. In 2023, 178 countries maintained legal barriers preventing women's full economic participation. Consequently, nearly 2.4 billion women worldwide do not enjoy the same financial rights as men. Following Pierre Bourdieu's words to instill more reliability in our premise:

The universal primacy given to men asserts itself in the objectivity of social structures and productive and reproductive activities based on a sexual division of labor, which grants men the better part [...]" (Bourdieu, 2012, p. 45).

This quote underscores the deeply ingrained societal structures that perpetuate gender inequality, making it clear that achieving gender equality is not just a matter of changing laws but also of transforming these fundamental social structures.

That said, structural issues continue to manifest in aspects related to sexual and reproductive health, political and legal representation, and economic disparity, among others. The situation becomes even more severe when considering the insufficiency of data and evidence linked to the variables involved in the broader debate on gender equality. Concerning the data necessary to monitor SDG 5 compliance, there is a 44% shortfall considering the average percentage of all involved countries. This data gap is a significant obstacle to achieving gender equality. Approximately 41 countries may have already completed or are close to achieving at least one SDG 5 indicator. Conversely, in 2023, more than 80 countries needed more data for at least one SDG 5 indicator (United Nations, 2023a, p. 12).

In the databases available in 120 countries and zones by 2023, 28 still needed laws guaranteeing women's rights in marriage or divorce. In 67 countries, there were no laws against direct or indirect discrimination against women. In 53 countries, laws did not specifically address equal pay for men and women performing the same function. Furthermore, even where such laws were in force, compliance appeared as a challenge in the document. (United Nations, 2023a, p. 14)

Given these frameworks, experts estimate that overcoming gender inequalities in 48 states, which account for 70% of the population of developing countries, will require \$64 billion per year until 2030. However, respective governments' investments have been far below the estimated total. (United Nations, 2023a, p. 13)

By 2030, progress must be 6.8 times faster than in 2023 to reduce to 5% the rate of women worldwide who are not studying or receiving training, nor are they inserted in the remunerated labor market. (United Nations, 2023a, p. 11)

The disparity between men and women is noteworthy regarding power relations and leadership positions. Women hold only 26.7% of parliamentary seats worldwide. In local governments, they account for 35.5%. Leadership and decision-making roles in the formal labor market comprise only 28.2%. In this particular aspect, the report published by the United Nations predicts that by 2050, this percentage will be 30% if we continue at the 2023 pace. (United Nations, 2023a, p. 15)

On average, worldwide, women dedicate 2.8 more hours per day than men to unpaid domestic and caregiving work. If we continue at the same pace, in 2050, we will see a very modest reduction. Women will spend 2.3 or 9,5% more hours daily on these tasks than men (United Nations, 2023a, p. 14).

Recommendations

- Establish a concept of gender that allows smooth transit through the intended areas, avoiding noise in the dialogues. As a suggestion: "[...] gender equality refers to equality in rights, responsibilities, and opportunities for women, men, and girls and boys. [...] To be fully achieved, it must include the specificities of black, Indigenous, quilombola, lesbian, bisexual women, and trans people, among others." (UN BR, 2016, p. 17)
- Repeal discriminatory legislation and enact laws leading to gender equality, prioritizing women and girls facing overlapping forms of discrimination.
- Invest and supervise public resources to implement laws and create gender-perspective policies since only 26% of the world's countries present these budget allocations. (United Nations, 2023a, p. 15)
- Address the causes of gender-based violence and support women's and girls' access to quality multisectoral programs.
- Ensure universal access to sexual health and reproductive rights since 44% of women aged 15 to 49, married or living with their partners, are prevented from exercising autonomy over their bodies. (United Nations, 2023a, p. 15)
- Guarantee that women, in all their diversity, fulfill leadership roles and occupy decision-making spaces.
- Promote the division of unpaid domestic and caregiving work based on gender equality.
- Form collaborative alliances between governments, civil society organizations, companies, and international entities to identify and remove barriers to gender equality.

Conclusions

Launched in 2015 with a view to its full implementation over the next 15 years, the 2030 Agenda regarding SDG 5, i.e., gender equality, runs the risk of not being fulfilled. The fact is that if we do not prioritize this Goal, given the transversal characteristic of gender equality, the entire Agenda will be compromised. From ending poverty (SDG 1) to zero hunger (SDG 2), good health and well-being (SDG 3), quality education (SDG 4), decent work and economic growth (SDG 8), reducing inequalities (SDG 10), peace, justice, and strong institutions (SDG 16), to partnerships to achieve the Goals (SDG 17) will be unfeasible as women and girls make up almost half of the world's population. (UNITED NATIONS 2024) To address this risk, tackling institutional barriers such as discriminatory laws, low participation of women in leadership and decision-making positions, and lack of investments aimed at gender equality at national, regional, and global levels need to be at the center of debates and investments.

In short, both active resistance and chronic disinvestment concerning gender equality lie behind the obstacles pointed out throughout our explanation. It is known, for example, that investment in job creation impacts all people. However, without a gender focus, we would fatally overlook issues related to discrimination and the full participation of women in the labor market. In this case, neglecting the gender factor could exacerbate rather than mitigate inequality. From an intersectional perspective, this inequality further aggravates as it invisibilizes the realities of millions of women and girls.

References

Bourdieu, Pierre (2012). A dominação masculina. Bertrand Brasil.

ONU BR (2016). Glossário de termos do Objetivo de Desenvolvimento Sustentável 5: Alcançar a igualdade de gênero e empoderar todas as mulheres e meninas. Nações Unidas no Brasil. Access 08/03/2024. Available <<https://www.onumulheres.org.br/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/Glossario-ODS-5.pdf>>.

ONU BR (2015). Objetivos de Desenvolvimento Sustentável / Igualdade de Gênero. Nações Unidas no Brasil. Access 08/01/2024. Available <<https://brasil.un.org/pt-br/sdgs/5>>.

UN (2023a). Progress on the Sustainable Development Goals: the gender snapshot 2023. UN Women. Access 08/03/2024. Available <<https://www.unwomen.org/en/digital-library/publications/2023/09/progress-on-the-sustainable-development-goals-the-gender-snapshot-2023>>.

UN (2023b). Goal 5: Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls. UN Sustainable Development Goals. Access 08/03/2024. Available <<https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/gender-equality/>>.

UN (2024). The 2024 revision of world population prospects. UN Secretariat - Department of Economic and Social Affairs. Access 08/03/2024. Available <<https://population.un.org/wpp/>>.

World Bank Group (2024). Women, Business and the Law 2024. International Bank for Reconstruction and Development / The World Bank. Access 08/01/2024. Available <<https://wbl.worldbank.org/en/wbl>>.

Yanatma, Servet (2024). Gender pay gap: this is the only country in Europe that pays women more than men. Euro News. Access 08/03/2024. Available <<https://www.euronews.com/next/2024/03/08/gender-pay-gap-in-europe-how-do-countries-compare-on-narrowing-the-divide>>.

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